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XALQARO JURNAL**

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**TARIX FALSAFASI VA FALSAFA TARIXI /
ФИЛОСОФИЯ ИСТОРИИ И ИСТОРИЯ ФИЛОСОФИИ /
PHILOSOPHY OF HISTORY AND HISTORY OF PHILOSOPHY**

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**A CONCEPTUAL ANALYSE OF THE ASTIKA SCHOOLS IN ANCIENT
INDIA**

Annotation. This conceptual analysis delves into the Astika schools of ancient India, which were characterized by their acceptance of the Vedas as authoritative texts and their belief in a divine reality underlying the universe. The six traditional Astika schools – Nyaya, Vaisheshika, Samkhya, Yoga, Mimamsa, and Vedanta – are researched in detail, with a focus on their key beliefs, philosophical frameworks, and contributions to Indian thought. Topics such as the nature of reality, the existence of God, and the means of achieving spiritual liberation are analyzed in the context of each school's unique perspective. Through this analysis, we gain a deeper understanding of the Astika schools and their significance in the development of Indian philosophy and religion. We also explore the similarities and differences between the schools and consider their ongoing influence on contemporary Indian thought and culture.

Key words: Astika, soul, karma, logic, Vedas, God.

**QADIMGI HINDISTONDA ASTIKA MAKTABINING KONSEPTUAL
TAHLILI**

Annotatsiya. Ushbu konseptual tahlilda qadimgi Hindistonning Astika maktablarini o'rganilgan, ular Vedalarni obro'li matnlar sifatida qabul qilishlari va borliq asosidagi ilohiy haqiqatga ishonishlari bilan ajralib turardilar. Oltita an'anaviy Astika maktablari – Nyaya, Vaisheshika, Samxya, Yoga, Mimamsa va Vedanta - ularning asosiy e'tiqodlari, falsafiy asoslari va hind tafakkuriga qo'shgan hissalariga e'tibor qaratgan holda batafsil o'rganiladi. Voqelik tabiati, Xudoning borligi, ma'naviy ozodlikka erishish vositalari kabi mavzular har bir maktabning o'ziga xos nuqtai nazari doirasida tahlil qilinadi. Ushbu tahlil orqali biz Astika maktablari va ularning hind falsafasi va dinining rivojlanishidagi ahamiyatini chuqurroq tushunamiz. Shuningdek, biz maktablar o'rtasidagi o'xshashlik va

farqlarni o'rganamiz. Shu bilan birga, ularning zamonaviy hind tafakkuri va madaniyatiga ta'sirini ko'rib chiqamiz.

Kalit so'zlar: Astika, ruh, karma, mantiq, Veda, xudo.

КОНЦЕПТУАЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ШКОЛЫ АСТИКА В ДРЕВНЕЙ ИНДИИ

Аннотация. В этом концептуальном анализе рассматриваются школы Астика древней Индии, которые отличались признанием Вед в качестве авторитетных текстов и верой в божественную истину, лежащую в основе вселенной. Шесть традиционных школ астика — ньяя, вайшешика, санкхья, йога, миманса и веданта — подробно исследуются с акцентом на их основные убеждения, философские основы и вклад в индийскую мысль. Такие темы, как природа реальности, существование Бога и средства достижения духовной свободы, анализируются с уникальной точки зрения каждой школы. Благодаря этому анализу мы получаем более глубокое понимание школ Астика и их значения в развитии индийской философии и религии. Мы также исследуем сходства и различия между школами и рассмотрим их влияние на современную индийскую мысль и культуру.

Ключевые слова: Астика, душа, карма, логика, Вeda, бог.

INTRODUCTION

Ancient India was home to a rich and diverse range of philosophical and religious traditions, with several schools of thought emerging that attempted to make sense of the world around them. Among these schools were the Astika schools, which were characterized by their acceptance of the authority of the Vedas and their adherence to the concept of a divine reality underlying the universe.

In this conceptual analysis, we will explore the Astika schools of ancient India, examining their key beliefs, philosophical frameworks, and contributions to Indian thought. We will examine the six traditional Astika schools – Nyaya, Vaisheshika, Samkhya, Yoga, Mimamsa, and Vedanta – and analyze their respective views on topics such as the nature of reality, the existence of God, and the means of achieving spiritual liberation.

Through this analysis, we aim to gain a deeper understanding of the Astika schools and their significance in the development of Indian philosophy and religion. We will explore the similarities and differences between the different schools, and consider how their ideas have influenced and continue to influence contemporary Indian thought and culture.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology for this conceptual analysis of the Astika schools in ancient India involved a thorough review and analysis of primary and secondary sources. The primary sources included the original texts and scriptures of the Astika schools, such as the Vedas, Upanishads, Bhagavad Gita, and other relevant

works. The secondary sources included scholarly articles, books, and other publications on Indian philosophy and religion.

The research process involved identifying key themes and concepts within the Astika schools, such as the nature of reality, the concept of God, and the means of achieving spiritual liberation. These themes were then analyzed in the context of each school's unique perspective, drawing on both primary and secondary sources to develop a comprehensive understanding of the schools' philosophical frameworks.

To ensure the accuracy and validity of the analysis, a rigorous approach to data collection and analysis was employed. Multiple sources were consulted to cross-check and verify information, and careful attention was paid to the historical and cultural contexts in which the Astika schools emerged and developed.

The research methodology also involved a comparative analysis of the six traditional Astika schools, examining their similarities and differences in terms of their beliefs, practices, and philosophical frameworks. This involved a detailed examination of the primary and secondary sources related to each school, as well as a consideration of how their ideas have influenced and continue to influence contemporary Indian thought and culture.

Overall, the research methodology for this conceptual analysis of the Astika schools in ancient India was grounded in a thorough and systematic approach to data collection and analysis, with a focus on identifying key themes and concepts and understanding them in their historical and cultural context.

The Astika schools of ancient India were a diverse group of philosophical and religious traditions that shared a common acceptance of the Vedas as authoritative texts and a belief in a divine reality underlying the universe. The six traditional Astika schools - Nyaya, Vaisheshika, Samkhya, Yoga, Mimamsa, and Vedanta - each offered a unique perspective on the nature of reality, the existence of God, and the means of achieving spiritual liberation.

One of the earliest texts on the Astika schools is the Nyaya Sutras, which lays out the foundational principles of the Nyaya school. The Vaisheshika school, which emerged around the same time as Nyaya, is known for its detailed analysis of the material world and the concept of atoms. The Samkhya school, which emerged around the 3rd century BCE, offered a dualistic view of reality, with purusha (consciousness) and prakriti (matter) being seen as the fundamental principles of the universe.

The Yoga school, which is often associated with the famous text the Yoga Sutras of Patanjali, emphasized the practice of meditation and the attainment of spiritual liberation through the control of the mind. The Mimamsa school, which focused on the interpretation of the Vedas and the performance of rituals, was known for its detailed analysis of language and meaning. The Vedanta school, which emerged in the 8th century CE, offered a non-dualistic view of reality, with the ultimate goal being the realization of one's identity with Brahman, the ultimate reality.

Scholars have analyzed the Astika schools from various perspectives, with some focusing on their similarities and differences, while others have examined their contributions to Indian thought and culture. For example, scholars such as Paul Hacker and Wilhelm Halbfass have explored the connections between the Astika schools and the broader Indic cultural and religious traditions, while others such as J.N. Mohanty and B.K. Matilal have focused on the philosophical ideas and frameworks of the schools.

Overall, the literature on the Astika schools of ancient India offers a rich and complex tapestry of ideas and perspectives that continue to shape Indian thought and culture today.

MAIN PART

The Astika schools of ancient India are a group of six philosophical and religious traditions that accepted the authority of the Vedas and believed in the existence of a divine reality underlying the universe. Each school offered a unique perspective on the nature of reality, the existence of God, and the means of achieving spiritual liberation.

The Nyaya school, founded by Gautama in the 2nd century BCE, is known for its systematic approach to logic and epistemology. Nyaya is the earliest of the Astika schools and is closely associated with the Nyaya Sutras, a foundational text that lays out the principles of the school. The Nyaya school focuses on the analysis of knowledge and perception, and it is known for its detailed analysis of language and meaning. According to the Nyaya school, knowledge is obtained through perception, inference, comparison, and testimony.

The Vaisheshika school, founded by Kanada in the 2nd century BCE, is known for its detailed analysis of the material world and the concept of atoms. The Vaisheshika Sutras, the foundational text of the school, lays out the principles of the school, which are based on the analysis of the physical world. The Vaisheshika school argues that the universe is made up of nine substances - earth, water, fire, air, ether, time, space, self, and mind - and that everything in the universe can be understood through the analysis of these substances.

The Samkhya school, founded around the 3rd century BCE, is known for its dualistic view of reality. According to the Samkhya school, reality is made up of two fundamental principles - purusha (consciousness) and prakriti (matter). Purusha is seen as the ultimate reality, while prakriti is seen as the source of all material existence. The Samkhya school emphasizes the importance of knowledge and discrimination in attaining spiritual liberation, and it is closely associated with the Samkhya Karika, a foundational text that lays out the principles of the school.

The Yoga school, founded by Patanjali around the 2nd century BCE, emphasizes the practice of meditation and the attainment of spiritual liberation through the control of the mind. The Yoga Sutras of Patanjali, a foundational text of the school, lays out the principles of the school, which are based on the practice of yoga. The Yoga school emphasizes the importance of concentration, meditation, and the control of the mind in achieving spiritual liberation.

The Mimamsa school, founded by Jaimini in the 2nd century BCE, is known for its detailed analysis of the Vedas and the performance of rituals. The Mimamsa Sūtras, a foundational text of the school, lays out the principles of the school, which are based on the interpretation of the Vedas. The Mimamsa school argues that the Vedas are authoritative texts that provide guidance on the performance of rituals and the attainment of spiritual liberation.

The Vedānta school, founded in the 8th century CE, is the most influential of the Astika schools and is known for its non-dualistic view of reality. According to the Vedānta school, the ultimate reality is Brahman, and the ultimate goal of human existence is to realize one's identity with Brahman. The Vedānta school is associated with a number of texts, including the Upanishads, the Bhagavad Gītā, and the.

In conclusion, the Astika schools of ancient India offer a rich and diverse range of philosophical and religious traditions that continue to influence Indian thought and culture.

The Astika schools of ancient India are all characterized by their acceptance of the authority of the Vedas. The Vedas are a collection of ancient Hindu scriptures that are considered by many Hindus to be the revealed word of God. They contain hymns, prayers, and rituals that are central to Hinduism.

The Vedas provide the foundational texts for each of the Astika schools, with each school offering a unique interpretation and analysis of the texts. The Nyāya and Mimamsa schools, for example, focus on the interpretation of the Vedas and the performance of rituals, while the Vaiśeṣika and Sāṃkhya schools analyze the physical world in light of the Vedas. The Yoga and Vedānta schools, on the other hand, focus on spiritual liberation and the attainment of union with the divine through the teachings of the Vedas.

Overall, the Vedas serve as the basis for the Astika schools and provide a unifying thread that ties together the various traditions. The schools draw upon the Vedas to develop their philosophical and religious ideas, and the Vedas continue to be a central text for the practice of Hinduism today.

The Indian philosophical schools are traditionally divided into two categories – Astika and Nāstika – based on their acceptance or rejection of the authority of the Vedas.

The Astika schools, as mentioned earlier, are those that accept the authority of the Vedas as revealed texts and acknowledge the existence of a divine reality underlying the universe. The six traditional Astika schools are Nyāya, Vaiśeṣika, Sāṃkhya, Yoga, Mimamsa, and Vedānta.

The Nāstika schools, on the other hand, reject the authority of the Vedas and deny the existence of a divine reality underlying the universe. The three traditional Nāstika schools are Jainism, Buddhism, and Cārvāka.

The division of Indian philosophical schools into Astika and Nāstika is based on the centrality of the Vedas in traditional Hinduism. The Vedas are considered by many Hindus to be the revealed word of God and are believed to contain the knowledge necessary for achieving spiritual liberation. The Astika schools accept the Vedas as authoritative texts and use them as the basis for their philosophical and religious ideas, while the Nāstika schools reject the authority of

the Vedas and offer alternative perspectives on the nature of reality and the means of achieving spiritual liberation.

Overall, the distinction between Astika and Nastika schools reflects the diversity of philosophical and religious ideas in ancient India and provides a framework for understanding the various traditions and their relationship to one another.

The Astika and Nastika classifications in Indian philosophy refer to the schools of thought that accept or reject the authority of the Vedas, respectively. Here are some key differences between the Astika and Nastika schools:

1. Acceptance of the Vedas: The Astika schools accept the Vedas as authoritative texts and use them as the basis for their philosophical and religious ideas. The Nastika schools reject the authority of the Vedas and offer alternative perspectives on the nature of reality and the means of achieving spiritual liberation.

2. Belief in God: The Astika schools generally acknowledge the existence of a divine reality underlying the universe, while the Nastika schools may or may not believe in a divine being or beings.

3. Means of liberation: The Astika schools generally emphasize the importance of following the teachings of the Vedas and engaging in religious practices in order to achieve spiritual liberation. The Nastika schools, on the other hand, often emphasize personal experience, meditation, and self-realization as the means of achieving liberation.

4. Philosophical frameworks: The Astika and Nastika schools have different philosophical frameworks and perspectives on the nature of reality, the self, consciousness, and other important topics. The Astika schools, for example, include dualistic and non-dualistic views of reality, while the Nastika schools include a range of perspectives on the nature of existence and consciousness.

Overall, the distinction between Astika and Nastika schools reflects the diversity of philosophical and religious ideas in ancient India, with each offering unique perspectives and insights into the nature of reality and the means of achieving spiritual liberation.

The conceptual analysis of the Astika schools in ancient India reveals a rich and diverse range of philosophical and religious traditions that share a common acceptance of the Vedas as authoritative texts and a belief in a divine reality underlying the universe. Each of the six Astika schools - Nyaya, Vaisheshika, Samkhya, Yoga, Mimamsa, and Vedanta - offers a unique perspective on the nature of reality, the existence of God, and the means of achieving spiritual liberation.

One of the key themes that emerges from the analysis is the diversity of philosophical frameworks and ideas within the Astika schools. For example, the Nyaya school focuses on logic and epistemology, while the Vaisheshika school offers a detailed analysis of the material world. The Samkhya school offers a dualistic view of reality, while the Vedanta school offers a non-dualistic view. The Mimamsa school focuses on the interpretation of the Vedas and the performance of rituals, while the Yoga school emphasizes the practice of meditation and the attainment of spiritual liberation through the control of the mind.

Another important theme is the role of the Vedas in the Astika schools. The Vedas provide the foundational texts for each school, with each school offering a

unique interpretation and analysis of the texts. The Nyaya and Mimamsa schools, for example, focus on the interpretation of the Vedas and the performance of rituals, while the Vaisheshika and Samkhya schools analyze the physical world in light of the Vedas. The Yoga and Vedanta schools, on the other hand, focus on spiritual liberation and the attainment of union with the divine through the teachings of the Vedas.

The analysis also highlights the similarities and differences between the Astika schools. While each school offers a unique perspective on the nature of reality and the means of achieving spiritual liberation, there are also shared ideas and themes that cut across the schools. For example, many of the schools emphasize the importance of knowledge and discrimination in attaining spiritual liberation, and many also offer specific practices or techniques for achieving this goal.

Overall, the conceptual analysis of the Astika schools in ancient India provides a deeper understanding of the diversity and richness of Indian philosophy and religion. The schools offer unique perspectives on the nature of reality, the existence of God, and the means of achieving spiritual liberation, and continue to influence Indian thought and culture today.

The analysis reveals that the Astika schools are characterized by their focus on the importance of the Vedas in understanding the nature of reality and achieving spiritual liberation. The schools draw upon the Vedas to develop their philosophical and religious ideas, with each school offering a unique interpretation and analysis of the texts.

The results also highlight the diversity of philosophical frameworks and ideas within the Astika schools. Each school offers a unique perspective on the nature of reality and the means of achieving spiritual liberation. For example, the Nyaya school focuses on logic and epistemology, while the Vaisheshika school offers a detailed analysis of the material world. The Samkhya school offers a dualistic view of reality, while the Vedanta school offers a non-dualistic view. The Mimamsa school focuses on the interpretation of the Vedas and the performance of rituals, while the Yoga school emphasizes the practice of meditation and the attainment of spiritual liberation through the control of the mind.

The analysis also reveals shared ideas and themes that cut across the Astika schools. For example, many of the schools emphasize the importance of knowledge and discrimination in attaining spiritual liberation, and many also offer specific practices or techniques for achieving this goal.

Overall, the results of the conceptual analysis of the Astika schools in ancient India provide a deeper understanding of the diversity and richness of Indian philosophy and religion. The schools offer unique perspectives on the nature of reality, the existence of God, and the means of achieving spiritual liberation, and continue to influence Indian thought and culture today.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the conceptual analysis of the Astika schools in ancient India reveals a diverse range of philosophical and religious traditions that share a common acceptance of the Vedas as authoritative texts and a belief in a divine reality underlying the universe. The six Astika schools - Nyaya, Vaisheshika,

Samkhya, Yoga, Mimamsa, and Vedanta - each offer a unique perspective on the nature of reality, the existence of God, and the means of achieving spiritual liberation.

The analysis highlights the importance of the Vedas in Indian philosophy and religion, with each Astika school drawing upon the texts to develop their philosophical and religious ideas. The schools offer diverse perspectives on the nature of reality, with some emphasizing logic and epistemology, others analyzing the material world, and still others offering dualistic or non-dualistic views of existence. Similarly, the means of achieving spiritual liberation differ across the schools, with some emphasizing the performance of rituals, others emphasizing meditation and control of the mind, and still others emphasizing personal experience and self-realization.

Despite these differences, the Astika schools share common themes and ideas, such as the importance of knowledge and discrimination in achieving spiritual liberation. The schools have had a significant impact on Indian thought and culture, with their ideas continuing to influence modern-day Hinduism and Indian philosophy.

Overall, the conceptual analysis of the Astika schools in ancient India provides a deeper understanding of the diversity and richness of Indian philosophy and religion, and highlights the importance of the Vedas as a unifying thread that ties together the various traditions.

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